

**Supplementary Information to paper entitled
“In Silico” Seawater**

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I. OPTIMIZED SOLUTE SAMPLES FOR MOLECULAR SIMULATIONS

The Reference Composition of “Standard Seawater” was defined¹ in terms of the mole fractions of the 15 major components based on the most accurate prior determinations of the composition. The stoichiometry was adjusted to achieve charge balance by making use of the 2005 atomic weights and finally rounded to 7 digits after the decimal point. Taking into account that the number of water molecules at the usual seawater salinities is about 50 times the total number of solute molecules, the sample required to match the Reference Composition would be of the order of 5×10^8 molecules. This is a prohibitive number for a molecular simulation run. It is then necessary to simplify the stoichiometry. In this work we made the assumption that a system considering only the six more abundant constituents could be able to account for the physico-chemical properties of seawater. These solutes (all of them are ionic compounds) represent a 99,7 percent of the mole fraction and the remainder 0,3 needs to be explicitly considered because it mostly corresponds to negatively charged molecules. Thus, we grouped together these minor components assigning them a negative charge.

The procedure to obtain a simplified sample is simple in principle. We may obtain more or less representative samples by multiplying the Reference Composition mole fractions by a factor and converting the resulting results to integer numbers. However, the real to integer numbers conversion distorts the input stoichiometry and, even more importantly, does not guarantee the charge neutrality of the sample. After analysing the ratios between the relative abundance of the constituents and a considerable trial and error we arrived at a composition totalising 318 ions that reproduced the Reference Composition of Standard Seawater with a root mean square deviation of only 0.0003. The agreement for a such a reduced sample is quite extraordinary so the finding was probably a lucky event not extendible to more complex samples. We thus decided to carry a systematic search of samples with optimal composition.

The first step of the is to choose a number of constituents. For instance, if we intend to consider explicitly only the ions whose mole fraction is greater than that of bicarbonate we fix this number to six. For a given set of components, we calculate the number of molecules of each type according to the mole fractions defined in the Reference Composition, x_{ref} . In particular, for sample sizes of 300 and 1000 solutes we obtain , see Table I, (146.2, 125.6, 14.2, 7.6, 2.8, 2.7) and (487.5, 418.8, 47.2, 25.2, 9.2, 9.1), respectively, yielding (146, 126, 14, 8, 3, 3) and (487, 419, 47, 25, 9, 9) ions when rounded to the nearest integers. Notice that these samples are not electrically neutral. We then define a new type of component (labelled as “Others” in Table I) and assign it the mole fraction needed to get a total mole fraction of 1 ($x_{others} = 0.00303$ when including explicitly 6 solutes). The number of molecules of this special solute type and its charge are calculated to ensure that the sample is electrically balanced. In our examples above, the number of “Others” molecules would be 1 and 3, carrying a negative charge in both cases. Using these numbers we calculate the actual mole fractions of the proposed samples. A reasonable measure of the quality of the sample is the root mean square of the deviations, *rmsd*, between the calculated and the reference mole fractions. These amount to 0.00175 and 0.00034 for 300 and 1000 ions, respectively.

As shown in the example above, increasing the sample size usually improves the agreement between the stoichiometry of the simplified seasalt sample and that of the Reference Composition. However, there are sample sizes that produce a closer agreement with a reduced number of ions. For instance, a sample of 318 ions leads to $rmsd = 0.00034$, five times smaller than that for 300 solute molecules and identical to that obtained for a 1000 ions sample. Thus, 318 ions should be considered an optimal choice for systems considering explicitly six components. We have carried out a systematic scanning of the sample sizes considering different number of components. Some of the resulting optimal samples are presented in Table I. There we use the notation $ISSS_{m,n}$, where ISSS is the acronym of “in silico” sea salt, m is the total number of solute molecules and n is the number of constituents explicitly included (the rest of components are grouped together as “Others”). Curiously, some sizes are optimal for different number of constituents. For instance, $ISSS_{1313,n}$ is optimal for $n = 6$ (not shown in I because $ISSS_{1631,6}$ is even better), 7 and 8.

Several factors limit effectually the use of a large number of components to represent the stoichiometry of seawater. The first one is the size of the system when water molecules are added to the seasalt composition. For normal ocean salinities a minimum of 15, 63, 193 and 630 thousands of molecules are required to include explicitly 6, 8, 10 and 13 components, respectively. But apart of the burden of generating initial configurations for the largest samples, the molecular simulation of these systems could be affordable. Molecular dynamics programs usually require small amounts of memory and larger system sizes allow to obtain statistically acceptable quantities with shorter simulation times. However, to ensure an equilibrated system the diffusion of the ions should allow, in principle, to explore many different ionic environments.

It is very likely that the preceding assertion would not be a real shortcoming in practice. Let us assume that we are interested in the determination of, for instance, the diffusivity of the fluoride ion in seawater. According to table I an optimal sample for a salinity $S = 35.16$ g/kg would be made of 629705 water and 13166 solute molecules. Among the latter, there would be just one strontium ion. Certainly, ensuring that the interactions between the single strontium and fluoride ions are statistically sampled would be an extremely costly task. But a poor sampling of these interactions has an almost nul effect in the diffusivity of the fluoride ion. It is clear that the effect of replacing the interactions of a single ion (strontium) by a another one with similar interatomic potential would be much smaller than the statistical uncertainty of the calculated diffusion coefficient even for

extremely long simulations. The same argument would probably be extensive to bicarbonate (only 20 ions in a sample of 630 thousand molecules!).

In fact, the main factor limiting the number of solutes explicitly included in the ISSS stoichiometry seems to be the availability of an accurate forcefield for the components. In the example above, instead of using a very detailed seasalt composition, it would be advisable to tune carefully the interactions of the fluoride anion with the most abundant seawater components, i.e. water, chloride and sodium. In the extreme case of the “Others” molecules such availability is impossible by definition. In order to look for optimal samples we need at least to assign them a charge. The neglected solutes in the ISSS_{*m,n*} samples with $n = 6, 8$ are mostly anions so we attribute them a negative charge. For $n = 10, 13$ the global charge of the excluded solutes is more or less balanced and we thus assume them to be neutral molecules.

II. RESIDENCE TIMES OF WATERS IN THE HYDRATION SHELL

Fig. II shows the average lifetime τ of the water molecules in the hydration shell of the seasalt ions at 15°C for two salinities, $S=35.16$ and $S=98.53$ g/kg. The residence time axis is represented in logarithmic scale to illustrate the exponential decay behavior at short times. Besides, this representation allows a better appreciation of the effect of the salinity. Numerical values of the lifetimes are given in table II. The lifetimes calculated using the short time exponential decay are quite similar to those obtained by integrating the correlation function (see the main paper) though the difference between them are systematic. These seems to indicate that the behavior at longer times may deviate slightly from the exponential decay.

FIG. 1. Residence times of water molecules in the hydration shell of the ions in seawater at 15°C for two different salinities. Left: cations; right: anions. Solid lines are the results at $S=35.16$ g/kg and dashed lines correspond to $S=98.53$ g/kg.

III. DEPENDENCE ON TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY OF THE SODIUM-CHLORIDE RDF'S

The Na-Cl radial distribution function (rdf) is presented in Figure III as a function of temperature and salinity. It resembles very much that of a simple NaCl solution at similar concentration using a force field closely related to that of this work.²

It shows a first peak which corresponds to what it is usually called contact ion pairs (CIP) and a second one denoting solvent separated ions pairs (SSIP). Our results indicate that most of the Na-Cl contacts are mediated by water molecules. As expected, an increase of the temperature favors the removal of some waters from the hydration layer. In this way, sodium and chloride ions may get more easily in close contact and the height of the CIP peak rises with temperature. However, the integration of the rdf to provide the number of CIP and SSIP indicates that, even at the highest temperature considered in this work, the sodium-chloride CIP are very rare. On the other hand, for a fixed temperature, the height of the rdf maxima decrease at increasing salt concentrations. This is a well-known, though counter-intuitive, result which can be explained by the increasing ionic shielding.

TABLE I. Optimized samples producing a close agreement with the Reference Composition of seasalt¹ using a reduced number of solute molecules. The upper row shows the total number of solute molecules (designed as ions for simplicity) in the sample. The columns labelled n and x are the number of ions and the corresponding mole fraction of each one. The latter may be compared with the mole fractions defined in the Reference Composition, x_{ref} . The root mean square of the deviations $x - x_{ref}$ for each sample is given in the row denoted as rms . The last row indicates the number of water molecules for a salinity $S = 35.16$ g/kg.

Notation	x_{ref}	ISSS _{318,6}		ISSS _{1631,6}		ISSS _{1313,7}		ISSS _{3371,7}		ISSS _{1313,8}		ISSS _{5871,8}		ISSS _{4047,10}		ISSS _{14480,10}		ISSS _{13166,13}		ISSS _{61313,13}	
		#ions	n	x	n	x	n	x	n	x	n										
Chloride	0.4874839	155	0.48742	795	0.48743	640	0.48743	1643	0.48739	640	0.48743	2862	0.48748	1973	0.48752	7059	0.48750	6418	0.48747	29889	0.48748
Sodium	0.4188071	133	0.41824	683	0.41876	550	0.41889	1412	0.41887	550	0.41889	2459	0.41884	1695	0.41883	6064	0.41878	5514	0.41881	25678	0.41880
Magnesium	0.0471678	15	0.04717	77	0.04721	62	0.04722	159	0.04717	62	0.04722	277	0.04718	191	0.04720	683	0.04717	621	0.04717	2892	0.04717
Sulfate	0.0252152	8	0.02516	41	0.02514	33	0.02513	85	0.02522	33	0.02513	148	0.02521	102	0.02520	365	0.02521	332	0.02522	1546	0.02521
Calcium	0.0091823	3	0.00943	15	0.00920	12	0.00914	31	0.00920	12	0.00914	54	0.00920	37	0.00914	133	0.00919	121	0.00919	563	0.00918
Potassium	0.0091159	3	0.00943	15	0.00920	12	0.00914	31	0.00920	12	0.00914	54	0.00920	37	0.00914	132	0.00912	120	0.00911	559	0.00912
Bicarbonate	0.0015340					2	0.00152	5	0.00148	2	0.00152	9	0.00153	6	0.00148	22	0.00152	20	0.00152	94	0.00153
Bromide	0.0007520									1	0.00076	4	0.00068	3	0.00074	11	0.00076	10	0.00076	46	0.00075
Boric acid	0.0002807													1	0.00025	4	0.00028	4	0.00030	17	0.00028
Carbonate	0.0002134													1	0.00025	3	0.00021	3	0.00023	13	0.00021
Borate	0.0000900																	1	0.00008	6	0.00010
Strontium	0.0000810																	1	0.00008	5	0.00008
Fluoride	0.0000610																	1	0.00008	4	0.00007
Others	0.0000157	1	0.00314	5	0.00307	2	0.00152	5	0.00148	1	0.00076	4	0.00068	1	0.00025	4	0.00028	0	0.00000	1	0.00002
$rmsd \times 10^4$		3.4		0.9		0.9		0.6		0.8		0.5		0.5		0.15		0.14		0.03	
#water		15214		78001		62791		161229		62785		280745		193537		692545		629705		2932449	

TABLE II. Number of water molecules in the hydration shell (HN) of the ionic components of seawater and their average lifetimes, τ (in ps). HN is calculated by integrating the ion- O_w distribution functions up to the first minimum, r_{min} . τ_{integ} and τ_{decay} are the values of the residence times evaluated by integration of the autocorrelation function of HN and its fit to an exponential decay, respectively. Data correspond to simulations at 15°C and two values of the salinity.

Ion	$S=35.16$ g/kg				$S=98.54$ g/kg			
	r_{min}	HN	τ_{integ}	τ_{decay}	r_{min}	HN	τ_{integ}	τ_{decay}
magnesium	0.315	6.00	-	1.4E5	0.315	6.02	-	0.9E5
calcium	0.325	7.43	114	116	0.322	7.46	118	119
sodium	0.315	5.53	18.2	18.6	0.316	5.53	19.4	20.0
sulfate	0.468	12.5	8.5	9.9	0.469	12.6	9.7	10.9
chloride	0.365	5.86	7.7	8.2	0.365	5.90	8.0	8.8
potassium	0.352	6.71	6.1	6.7	0.354	6.69	6.5	7.3

FIG. 2. Na-Cl radial distribution functions. Left: as a function of temperature for $S=35.16$ g/kg; right: as a function of salinity for $t=15^\circ\text{C}$.

IV. EFFECT OF MODIFYING THE NUMBER OF COMPONENTS OF THE SEASALT

In this section we compare the results for the compositions $\text{ISSS}_{318,6}$ and $\text{ISSS}_{318,4}$. The latter is obtained by replacing the potassium and calcium ions of the former by sodium and magnesium ions, respectively. We anticipate that the differences between the results of both systems at the same thermodynamic conditions are quite small, hardly detected in a graphical representation, so we will provide a numerical presentation of the results.

Table IV shows the volumes of the $\text{ISSS}_{318,6}$ and $\text{ISSS}_{318,4}$ systems at different temperatures and salinities. The differences between the results at $S = 35.16$ g/kg are very small, less than 0.1 nm^3 ($< 0.02\%$!) though larger than the combined statistical error (the estimated uncertainty of the results of a run, evaluated using block averages,³ is about 0.02 nm^3). The volumes for the $\text{ISSS}_{318,4}$ samples at $S = 35.16$ g/kg are smaller than those of the $\text{ISSS}_{318,6}$ system at all the temperatures but the differences are similar in the range of temperatures investigated. Increasing the salinity at constant temperature (15°C) increases the departures between both sample sets. However the differences remain quite small, the relative deviation being smaller than a 0.04 percent. In summary, the substitution of potassium and calcium ions by anions with the same electric charge leads to an almost insignificant but detectable increase in density.

The effect of the simplification of the ionic sample on the shear viscosity is presented in table IV. The estimated uncertainty of the results is less than a 1.5%. Thus, the differences between the calculated viscosities of the $\text{ISSS}_{318,6}$ and $\text{ISSS}_{318,4}$ samples are within the combined error of both simulations.

Figure IV shows a comparison of the Na-Cl distribution functions for the systems $\text{ISSS}_{318,6}$ and $\text{ISSS}_{318,4}$ at the same temperature and salinity. It may be seen that the rdf is almost insensitive to the this modification of the salt composition. In fact, the difference respect to the rdf in a single salt NaCl solution is also barely appreciable. In summary, the presence of small amounts of additional ions have a negligible effect on the Na-Cl distribution function.

TABLE III. Volumes (in nm^3) for the ISSS_{318,6} composition compared to solutions where the potassium and calcium ions are replaced by sodium and magnesium ions, respectively (ISSS_{318,4}). All the systems contain 15210 water molecules so that $S = 35.16$ g/kg for the systems with 318 ions. The systems at $S = 67.93$ g/kg (98.53 g/kg) contain the same number of water molecules but duplicate (triplicate) the number of ions in the sample.

t (°C)	salinity (g/kg)	ISSS _{318,6}	ISSS _{318,4}
-10	35.2	458.54	458.46
15	35.2	459.48	459.43
80	35.2	473.72	473.66
15	35.2	459.48	459.43
15	67.9	464.21	464.12
15	98.5	469.25	469.08

TABLE IV. Shear viscosities (in mPa s) for the ISSS_{318,6} composition compared to solutions where the potassium and calcium ions are replaced by sodium and magnesium ions, respectively (see tableIV for a more detailed description of the compositions of each system).

t (°C)	salinity (g/kg)	ISSS _{318,6}	ISSS _{318,4}
15	17.9	1.145	1.125
15	35.2	1.22	1.23
15	67.9	1.38	1.37
15	98.5	1.55	1.57
-10	35.2	2.735	2.73
15	35.2	1.22	1.23
80	35.2	0.392	0.400

FIG. 3. Na-Cl radial distribution function for the ISSS_{318,6} and ISSS_{318,4} compositions at $s=35.16$ g/kg. The curve labelled as Na-Cl refers to a pure NaCl solution with the same number of water molecules and occupying the same volume as the ISSS_{318,6} solution.

Notice that potassium and calcium ions are relatively abundant components of seawater, together they represent a 1.8% of the sea salt. Thus, the effect of considering explicitly less abundant species like the bicarbonate and bromide anions would much more difficult to be detected in molecular simulations since they only represent a 0.2% of the sea salt. In fact, it is very likely that the effect of the incorporation of these ions to the simulated system would be comparable or even smaller than the uncertainty of the experimental measurements.

V. COMPARISON WITH THE RESULTS FOR OTHER FORCEFIELDS

In this section we compare the results obtained using different parameters for the molecular interactions. A good model for water is of paramount importance so we have performed all the simulations with TIP4P/2005.⁴ For the ionic solutes, in addition to the Madrid-2019 forcefield, we have employed the OPLS forcefield as defined

TABLE V. Comparison to experimental measurements of the shear viscosities (in mPa s) at $S = 35.16$ g/kg calculated with the Madrid-2019 and the JC force field.

t ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	JC	Madrid-2019	Expt.
0	2.07	1.892	1.906
25	1.04	0.960	0.959
60	0.58	0.517	0.509

in the Gromacs package with the exception of the sulfate anion for which we have selected the Cannon et al.⁵ potential parameters. The more important components of seasalt are the sodium and chloride ions. The third forcefield only differs from the OPLS one in the interactions involving those ions which are represented by the Joung-Cheatham (JC) parameters⁶.

FIG. 4. Density as a function of temperature for seawater at $S = 35.16$ g/kg using the Madrid-2019, the OPLS and the Joung-Cheatham forcefields (see the text for details.)

The densities predicted by these forcefields for a salinity $S = 35.15$ g/kg are shown in Fig V. Overall the Madrid-2019 model performs much better than the OPLS and JC ones. The predictions of the former are excellent at low to medium temperatures though it degrades slightly at high temperatures. The JC forcefield exhibits the opposite behavior. Their predicted densities are sensibly different from the experimental ones at low to medium temperatures but the discrepancies decrease with increasing temperatures. Eventually, at 80°C , the performance of the JC model is slightly better than that of the Madrid-2019 forcefield. Finally, the predictions of the OPLS forcefield are clearly below the experiment throughout the entire range of temperatures of the liquid state.

As to the shear viscosity, data in Table V indicates that the performance of the Madrid-2019 force field is much better than that of the JC model at all the temperatures investigated for $S = 35.16$ g/kg.

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